

1 **Effect of Traffic Separation and Nature Integration on Affect and Cerebral**
2 **Oxygenation During Active Transport: An Immersive Virtual Reality and**
3 **Multi-Study Design**

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The study data and materials will be shared openly as part of the publication of the article. The proposed protocol has been reviewed and accepted by the ethics committee of the University of Lille (ref. 2025-968-S144). The proposed protocol has and will receive financial support from the University of Lille and from the City of Lille (MEL – Sensefit 2024-2027). The authors have no competing financial interests to declare.

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Abstract

26
27 Increasing active transport, such as walking or cycling, is key to reducing human-driven
28 greenhouse gas emissions and improving health outcomes. To facilitate the transition
29 from private cars to active transport, it is crucial to create urban environments that
30 induce positive experiences of active transportation, fostering positive affective
31 memories and increasing the intention to use these modes in the future. The proposed
32 programmatic registered report aims to investigate whether integrating traffic
33 separation and nature integration into urban concrete environments during active
34 transport sessions (i.e., cycling [Study 1] or walking [Study 2]) would improve the
35 affective experience and result in changes to cerebral oxygenation. A minimum of 36
36 adults will take part in three 15-min, moderate-intensity cycling ($n = 18$; Study 1) or
37 walking ($n = 18$; Study 2) sessions. These sessions will involve three different virtual
38 environments using the Meta Quest 3 headset: (a) an urban environment without traffic
39 separation; (b) an urban environment with traffic separation; and (c) an urban
40 environment with traffic separation and natural features. Affective valence will be
41 measured six times during each session using self-report questionnaires. To assess the
42 neural mechanisms underlying cognitive effort in relation to physical activity,
43 haemodynamic responses in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC) will be
44 monitored using multichannel functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS)
45 throughout the sessions. Remembered pleasure will be measured after each session,
46 using self-reported questionnaires. It is hypothesised that the separation of motorised
47 and non-motorised traffic in an urban concrete environment will lead to higher affective
48 valence (H_1) and remembered pleasure (H_2), as well as lower cerebral oxygenation of the
49 dlPFC (H_3). We expect this effect to be magnified by the inclusion of natural features.
50 Pilot data ($n = 9$) indicated that the protocol was considered to be acceptable ($M =$
51 5.74 ± 1.30 out of 9), with low-to-moderate cybersickness reported ($M = 33.92\% \pm$
52 19.64), indicating that virtual scenes and body movements were well synchronised. The
53 findings are expected to advance the theoretical understanding of how environmental
54 influences impact affective variables and prefrontal activation. This experimental

55 research will pave the way for future empirical studies, such as randomised controlled
56 trials, examining how urban design can facilitate the transition to active transport.

57 *Keywords:* cerebral oximetry; cycling; physical activity; prefrontal activity;
58 walking

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62 **Introduction**

63 The mid-20s saw a phenomenal increase in global socio-economic (e.g.
64 population, transport) and Earth system (e.g. carbon dioxide, surface temperature)
65 trends, known as the Great Acceleration (Steffen et al., 2015). Although controversial,
66 this period marks the period of the Anthropocene, an unofficial unit of geological time
67 that represents an interval of overwhelming human impact on the planet (Zalasiewicz
68 et al., 2024). In particular, the increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from human
69 activities has severe negative impacts on planet warm, water availability and food
70 production, biodiversity and ecosystems, health and well-being, and urban
71 infrastructure (IPCC, 2023; Nations, 2015; Ripple et al., 2021; Steffen et al., 2015). At
72 the individual level, shifting from the use of private car to active transport—such as
73 walking or cycling—represents one of the most effective strategies for reducing GHG
74 emissions in urban environments (Bernard et al., 2021; Chevance et al., 2023). In
75 addition, engaging in active transport has important health and economic benefits, such
76 as reducing the prevalence of chronic diseases and hospital expenditure (Chevance
77 et al., 2023; Gravett & Mundaca, 2021; Moutet et al., 2025). Despite these benefits,
78 studies show that distances between 3 and 5 km, which can be covered by bicycle in
79 15–20 minutes, account respectively for 30% and 50% of car journeys in Europe
80 (Chevance et al., 2023; Neves & Brand, 2019; Organization, 2022). The development of
81 interventions to increase the use of active transport is therefore warranted. In
82 particular, physical activity behaviour change frameworks could be mobilised to address
83 this research agenda, as active transport is a physical activity domain (Quinn &
84 Barone Gibbs, 2023).

85 The socio-cognitive approach remains the dominant framework to improve
86 engagement and maintenance of physical activity behaviour (Rhodes et al., 2019). This
87 approach posits that peoples' choices are influenced by a deliberate and rational

88 assessment of the potential advantages and disadvantages of intended actions, as well as
89 the likelihood of achieving these advantages (Rhodes et al., 2019). In the context of
90 active transport, systematic reviews and meta-analyses have revealed inconsistent
91 effects of socio-cognitive interventions in reducing car use and increasing active
92 transport. For example, Arnott et al. (2014) found no evidence that such interventions
93 reduce car use or increase active transport. In contrast, Semenescu et al. (2020)
94 reported a 7% reduction in car use when interventions targeted knowledge and
95 awareness, capability and self-efficacy, and social, cultural and moral norms. Finally, an
96 umbrella review further highlighted that socio-cognitive factors (e.g., social norms,
97 attitudes) are more strongly associated with intentions to adopt low-carbon travel
98 modes than with actual behaviour change (Javaid et al., 2020). Therefore, while
99 targeting socio-cognitive factors appears to be a promising approach to promoting
100 active transport use, it is not sufficient on its own.

101 In this context, recent advancements in the paradigm of affectivism argue for the
102 integration of affective variables into traditional socio-cognitive models to enhance our
103 understanding of cognition and behaviours (Dukes & Sander, 2024; Dukes et al., 2021;
104 Ferrer & Gillman, 2023). For example, Stevens et al. (2019) show that anticipated
105 affective reactions contribute to the explanatory variance of intentions to engage in
106 health risk behaviours among US adults. In this perspective, the Affect and Health
107 Behaviour Framework (AHBF Stevens et al., 2020; Williams & Evans, 2014) proposes
108 an organisational framework that includes affective variables (e.g., core affect,
109 remembered and anticipated pleasure), socio-cognitive variables (e.g., self-efficacy,
110 intention), environmental variables (e.g., behavioural cues), and motivations for
111 competing behaviours (e.g., driving a car versus cycling). The interplay among these
112 variables is thought to influence the engagement in physical activity behaviours (Conroy
113 & Berry, 2017; Rhodes et al., 2023; Stevens et al., 2020; Williams & Evans, 2014). For
114 example, Rhodes et al. (2023) showed that affective valence (i.e., pleasure-displeasure)
115 during and after an exercise session, along with affective judgements towards physical
116 activity, predicted intention to engage in physical activity, which in turn predicted

117 self-reported physical activity in postpartum women. These affective variables also have
118 the potential to mitigate the perceived exertion associated with physical activity.

119 To further extend these frameworks, the Theory of Effort Minimisation in
120 Physical Activity (Cheval & Boisgontier, 2021; Cheval et al., 2024) posits that humans
121 have a natural evolutionary tendency to minimise physical effort in order to conserve
122 energy resources. This tendency to minimise effort is an automatic incentive that can
123 override the intention to be physically active (Cheval & Boisgontier, 2021; Maltagliati
124 et al., 2025b). According to this model, positive affective experiences associated with
125 physical activity could help reduce the perceived effort involved and thus facilitate
126 engagement with and maintenance of this practice throughout life (Maltagliati et al.,
127 2025a). For example, a person who enjoys cycling to work will perceive less effort and
128 be more inclined to repeat the experience, compared to someone who dislikes cycling.
129 Thus, improving the affective experience of active transport is warranted.

130 Together, these frameworks offer a comprehensive model for understanding
131 physical activity behaviours. While the AHBF takes a holistic view of how affective,
132 cognitive and environmental factors influence decisions about physical activity, the
133 TEMPA goes further by specifically addressing the role of effort in behaviour regulation.

134 It has been argued that environmental factors play a critical role in enhancing
135 the affective experience of physical activity and promoting the adoption of active
136 transport (Fessler et al., 2024; Javaid et al., 2020; Jones & Zenko, 2023). For instance, a
137 narrative review by Bourke et al. (2021) showed that outdoor physical activity elicits
138 more positive self-reported affective valence than indoor activity, particularly when
139 conducted in natural environments. This finding is supported by a recent meta-analysis
140 indicating that enjoyment levels are significantly higher during outdoor exercise when
141 compared to indoor exercise (Peddie et al., 2024). In the context of active transport, the
142 major environmental factors associated with its usage include walkability, bikeability,
143 perceived safety and weather (Javaid et al., 2020; Mengiste et al., 2025). For example,
144 the separation of motorised and non-motorised transport modes through infrastructure
145 such as bike lanes and pavement has been demonstrated to improve perceived safety

146 and pleasure during active travel (Cambra & Moura, 2020; Timmons et al., 2024).
147 Additionally, the integration of natural elements, such as trees and green spaces, in
148 urban environments can further improve pleasantness (Basu et al., 2022).

149 Mechanistic explanations suggest that green environments may trigger our
150 innate tendency to respond positively to nature, thereby increasing our sense of safety
151 and reducing the cognitive effort required to overcome potential threats (García-Martín
152 et al., 2025; Kaplan, 1992; Staats et al., 2003). This is supported by neurobiological
153 evidence showing lower beta activity during walks in urban green spaces compared to
154 busy urban areas, which may be attributed to lower demands on attention and vigilance
155 (Neale et al., 2020). Furthermore, converging evidence from
156 electroencephalography (EEG), functional magnetic resonance imaging (*fMRI*), and
157 functional near-infrared spectroscopy (*fNIRS*) studies have demonstrated that exposure
158 to nature tends to induce lower activation of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC),
159 a brain region involved in attentional control, effort processing, and cognitive effort
160 (Causse et al., 2017; Gerber et al., 2025), when compared to urban environments
161 (Bolouki, 2023; Geissler et al., 2021). For instance, Geissler et al. (2021) found that
162 driving in the countryside resulted in lower dlPFC oxygenation than urban driving,
163 indicating reduced mental workload — a component of cognitive effort. While these
164 findings provide important preliminary evidence, further research is needed to examine
165 these effects specifically in active transport contexts.

166 Neurobiological data can provide critical insights into the brain correlates
167 underlying cognitive effort, complementing traditional self-report and behavioural
168 measures, which are often limited by social desirability or recall bias (Corneille &
169 Gawronski, 2024). In the field of physical activity, *fNIRS* is increasingly used to
170 measure cerebral oxygenation, providing real-time, non-invasive, and spatially localised
171 measurements of tissue oxygenation dynamics with high tolerance to motion artefacts
172 (Hammond, 2011; Leff et al., 2011; Perrey et al., 2024). For example, Jones and
173 Ekkekakis (2019) demonstrated that greater right dlPFC oxygenation during
174 moderate-intensity cycling was associated with lower affective valence in participants

175 who preferred low-intensity exercise. These results suggest that pleasurable experiences
176 may reduce the need for cognitive control. Thus, investigating the brain correlate of
177 cognitive effort is warranted to better understand the mechanisms underlying the effect
178 of the environment on pleasure, perceived exertion and cognitive effort.

179 Although naturalistic testing provides valuable insights into real-world
180 behaviour, it remains fraught with complexities that challenge the rigour and reliability
181 of research findings in the physical activity context (Gerwann et al., 2025). Ecological
182 environments can present challenges for data collection and replicability due to
183 unpredictable environmental factors (e.g., car and pedestrian traffic) and variable
184 natural conditions. Furthermore, the absence of a controlled environment makes it
185 difficult to isolate and measure the impact of specific variables, such as the addition or
186 removal of particular natural features from an urban environment. However, by
187 immersing participants in VR and incorporating multisensory features such as sounds
188 and odours, researchers can create controlled laboratory settings that closely resemble
189 ecological environments (Gerwann et al., 2025). For example, Batistatou et al. (2022)
190 used virtual reality (VR) to examine how vegetation in an urban environment impact
191 the affective experience and the cognitive effort of walking. Results showed that adding
192 natural features (e.g. trees) to an urban concrete environment during a pedestrian
193 walking leads to more positive affective valence. However, the authors did not report a
194 significant effect of the condition on cognitive effort, as measured by the number of
195 blinks per minute. They speculated that this measure may not be sensitive enough in a
196 VR setting to detect differences. Thus, the use of a more sensitive, VR-compatible
197 measure of cognitive effort, such as *f*NIRS, is required. For example, Jones and Wheat
198 (2023) measured dlPFC activity during a high-intensity cycling sessions, using a
199 combined VR-*f*NIRS setting. Results showed that a VR natural environment,
200 accompanied by a nature soundtrack, was associated with less dlPFC activity compared
201 to a visually and auditorily sterile control environment.

202 Taken together, these results suggest that separating motorised and
203 non-motorised transport modes has the potential to make active transport more

204 enjoyable and less cognitively demanding. Furthermore, the addition of natural features
205 may magnify these effects. However, previous empirical studies suffer from limitations
206 that hinder definitive conclusions. First, most studies treat natural and urban
207 environments as separate conditions (e.g., nature vs. city), rather than examining how
208 integrating natural elements into existing urban settings might influence affective and
209 neurobiological responses during active transport (e.g., Bolouki, 2023; Geissler et al.,
210 2021; Peddie et al., 2024). In addition, no study have formally tested the effect of traffic
211 separation on dlPFC activity. Consequently, the potential impact of combining traffic
212 separation and natural features within the same urban environment on affective and
213 neurobiological responses remains unclear. Second, prior EEG and fNIRS studies
214 studies have primarily focused on walking (e.g., Bolouki, 2023; Neale et al., 2020),
215 leaving a gap in understanding the neurobiological correlates of cognitive effort during
216 other active transport mode (e.g., cycling). Third, while traffic separation appears to
217 enhance pleasure in pedestrian contexts (Cambra & Moura, 2020), its effect on cyclists
218 remains ambiguous. For example, although Javaid et al. (2020)'s systematic review
219 suggests that separated bicycle infrastructure decrease perceived stress and produce
220 more positive feeling, Xing et al. (2018) found that perceptions of bicycle infrastructure
221 (e.g., bike lanes) are not related to bicycling affect (i.e., liking of bicycling). Thus, the
222 effect of traffic separation on affective experiences during cycling remains unclear. In
223 summary, further research is needed to investigate how the simultaneous
224 implementation of traffic separation and natural elements in urban environments
225 influences affective and cognitive responses during active transport.

226 **Objectives and Hypotheses**

227 For both studies, we hypothesise that a clear separation of motorised and
228 non-motorised traffic in an urban concrete environment will lead to higher affective
229 valence (H_1) and remembered pleasure (H_2), as well as lower cerebral oxygenation of
230 the dlPFC (H_3). We expect these effects to be amplified by the inclusion of natural
231 features, as previous research suggests that such elements provide restorative benefits
232 that may counterbalance any increased perceptual complexity from additional visual

233 stimuli (Bolouki, 2023; Geissler et al., 2021; Neale et al., 2020). Exploratory analyses
234 will be conducted to examine the effect of conditions on various outcomes, including
235 affective (e.g. anticipated pleasure), psychophysical (e.g. perceived exertion),
236 socio-cognitive (e.g. self-efficacy and intention), and psychophysiological (e.g. HRV)
237 variables, as well as the interplay between these variables. These analyses will allow us
238 to examine whether patterns across variables converge or diverge, thereby supporting a
239 more integrative interpretation of the results. As Stage 1 registered reports should not
240 include exploratory analysis, these will only be described in Stage 2.

241

Methods

242 Participants

243 Volunteer adults will be eligible if they are (a) aged 18–50, (b) have normal or
244 corrected-to-normal vision, (c) have no contraindications to moderate-intensity physical
245 activity, and (d) have no motor dysfunction, neurological or psychiatric disorders,
246 colour blindness, auditory impairment or anosmia. As the primary focus of our
247 intervention is to encourage individuals to adopt active transport for commuting, we
248 will exclude participants who already cycle (Study 1) or walk (Study 2) for their daily
249 commute. Moderate physical activity intensity is defined as an intensity below the first
250 ventilatory threshold (i.e., the activity must be slightly tiring, breathing accelerates, but
251 it is still possible to hold a conversation without interruption, Bok et al., 2022; Mezzani
252 et al., 2013). Participants will be compensated for their time (i.e., €30 for the
253 completion of the full procedure). To enhance the representativeness of our sample, we
254 will target employed adults rather than university students by collaborating with local
255 organisations, including the Maison des Mobilités Durables in Lille, the Roubaix
256 Sustainable Development Department, and the Tourcoing Sustainable Development
257 Mission.

258 Study Design and Power Analysis

259 The present multi-study uses a fully counterbalanced, repeated-measures and
260 crossover design. Due to the inherently visual nature of the conditions under study, it is
261 not possible to blind participants and experimenters to the conditions. However, the

262 participants will remain unaware of the purpose and hypotheses of the study. Eligible
263 participants will take part in three 15-minute, moderate-intensity cycling (Study 1) or
264 walking (Study 2) sessions during a single laboratory visit, totalling 45 minutes. These
265 sessions will involve three different virtual environments: (a) a non-separated
266 traffic (NS) condition; (b) a separated traffic (S) condition; and (c) a separated traffic
267 with natural features (SN) condition. To enhance immersion, a congruent sonic and
268 odour environment will be provided. Odours will be diffused continuously throughout
269 each session using olfactory speakers (Olfahome E140, OdoraVision; for a similar
270 procedure, see Coeugnet et al., 2025). The sonic environment will be played through the
271 VR headset. Participants will be randomly assigned by the experimental team to one of
272 6 possible sequences of the three conditions, following Williams' procedure (Williams,
273 1949). The randomisation will be conducted using R (v.4.5.1), with the code available
274 on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658559>).

275 The *a priori* power analysis was based on the linear mixed-effects
276 models (LMMs) used to test the effect of conditions on affective valence (H_1),
277 remembered pleasure (H_2), and cerebral oxygenation of the dlPFC (H_3). In fully
278 counterbalanced designs—such as the one employed in this study—repeated-measures
279 ANOVA and LMMs are nearly identical. This similarity arises because, under balanced
280 conditions, the distribution of test statistics under the alternative hypothesis for both
281 approaches follows a non-central F-distribution, with a non-centrality parameter derived
282 from the fixed effects and variance components of the model (for the related equation,
283 see Parma et al., 2023). Thus, we used a one-way within-subjects repeated-measures
284 ANOVA on G*Power (v. 3.1; Faul et al., 2009) to estimate the required sample size for
285 the critical LMM-based statistical tests in this study. As a precautionary measure, we
286 conducted further power analyses using the SIMR R package (Green & MacLeod, 2016),
287 simulating data based on the fixed and random effect parameters estimated from our
288 design. The residual variance (σ^2) and the random intercept parameters (SD) were
289 based on a conservative version of the parameters from Brevers et al. (2024)'s study,
290 who used LMMs to test the effect of their conditions on remembered pleasure ($\sigma^2 = 1.0$

291 and $SD = 0.60$). The R code and the output of the power simulations are openly
292 available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658559>).

293 The calculation was based on the smallest effect sizes reported in prior studies
294 involving adults (Batistatou et al., 2022; Cambra & Moura, 2020; Focht, 2013; Geissler
295 et al., 2021), using an alpha level of .05 and a desired power of .90. To formally model
296 the correction for publication bias and use a more conservative effect size estimate, we
297 performed a safeguard power analysis (Lakens, 2022; Perugini et al., 2014) using the
298 lower bound of the 60% two-sided confidence interval around the effect size estimate
299 (see R script for details of calculation, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658559>). For
300 H_1 , a minimum of 15 ($f = 0.43$; Cambra & Moura, 2020) and 12 participants ($f = 0.48$;
301 Batistatou et al., 2022) will be required to detect an effect of the S and SN conditions
302 on affective valence, respectively. For H_2 , a minimum of 15 participants will be required
303 to detect an effect of both conditions on remembered pleasure ($f = 0.43$; Cambra &
304 Moura, 2020; Focht, 2013). As our design is fully counterbalanced across three
305 conditions (six possible sequences), the sample size should be a multiple of six. Thus, 18
306 participants will be required for H_1 and H_2 . For H_3 , a minimum of six participants will
307 be required to detect an effect of both conditions on cerebral oxygenation in the dlPFC
308 ($f = 1.93$; Geissler et al., 2021). Similar results were found for all hypotheses using the
309 SIMR R package method (see Supplementary Material 1). Due to the limited number of
310 studies exploring this research question, the extant literature does not clearly specify
311 any differences between cycling and walking with regard to our variables of interest and
312 study design. Consequently, the effect sizes utilised for sample calculation in both
313 studies will be identical. It should be noted that, even when a safeguard power analysis
314 is performed, using the effect size from previous studies can introduce biases. Therefore,
315 we aim to recruit as many participants as possible within our time and resource
316 constraints (Lakens, 2022). Any excluded participant will be replaced to ensure a
317 minimum of $n = 18$ per study..

318 **Procedure**

319 All the outcomes and the assessment method are detailed in Supplementary
320 Material 2.

321 *Baseline Testing*

322 The study will consist of three sessions within one laboratory visit. Participants
323 will be advised to refrain from consuming caffeine and cigarettes for 12 and 2 hours
324 before testing, respectively (Cheval et al., 2022; Heilbronner et al., 2015; Kennedy &
325 Haskell, 2011). After recruitment and the signed consent form, participants will
326 complete a questionnaire measuring demographic (e.g., date of birth, gender,
327 socio-economic status), motivational (e.g., intention towards active transport,
328 approach-avoidance tendencies towards effort), affective (e.g., affective attitudes
329 towards active transports, baseline core affect), and behavioural (e.g., active transport
330 use) variables. Anthropometric data (i.e., height, weight) will be self-reported. Previous
331 experience with VR, caffeine and cigarette consumption before the session, and sleep
332 quality from the previous night will be reported by the participants.

333 *Habituation Procedure*

334 Before the first session begins, participants will undergo a 5-minute habituation
335 procedure to familiarise themselves with the virtual environment and the questionnaires,
336 and to set the session intensity. They will be instructed to pedal on the bike (Study 1)
337 or walk on the treadmill (Study 2) at a wattage or speed that corresponds to moderate
338 intensity. Recently, self-reported subjective methods, such as the Talk Test (Foster
339 et al., 2018), has been proposed as an easy, ready-to-use and valid alternative for
340 exercise prescription (Bok et al., 2022). Specifically, participants will be asked to read a
341 40-word text aloud and answer the question “Was talking comfortable?” using a 1–10
342 visual analogue scale (Orizola-Cáceres et al., 2021). Moderate intensity corresponds to
343 the last stage where talking is "very easy" (2–3 out of 10). Participants will self-pace the
344 power, revolution per minute (RPM) and speed during the sessions to remain within the
345 moderate intensity range based on the talk test. Note that, the researcher will examine
346 these data, along with perceived exertion, in real time to check whether participants

347 deviate from the moderate intensity range (e.g. a perceived exertion score of >3). If a
348 deviation is observed, the researcher will instruct the participant to reduce the intensity.

349 ***Experimental Procedure***

350 Participants will begin the first 15-minute, moderate-intensity session following
351 the habitation procedure. The conditions will be administered in a fully
352 counterbalanced order. The following instructions will be provided to participants
353 before each condition: "During this session, you will cycle (or walk) for 15 minutes to
354 simulate travelling from your home to your workplace. Maintain a moderate pace that
355 allows you to move comfortably without getting out of breath — imagine you are
356 commuting to work as usual. You can look around or focus on the path, but keep a
357 steady pace throughout the session."

358 The virtual environment will be standardised across all conditions to control for
359 weather-related variability and its influence on our variables (Denissen et al., 2008; Hall
360 et al., 2012). Specifically, all conditions will feature a consistent meteorological setting
361 of a clear blue sky, no precipitation and mild sunlight.

362 **In-Task Measures.** A visual overview of the study procedure is presented in
363 Figure 1.

364 **Questionnaires Data.** During each session, core affect (Feeling Scale FS
365 and Felt Arousal Scale FAS; Hardy and Rejeski, 1989; Svebak and Murgatroyd, 1985)
366 and rating of perceived exertion (RPE; Borg Category Ratio-10 scale [CR10]; Borg,
367 1998) will be measured six times (i.e., every two minutes from Minute 2 to Minute 12).
368 To minimise the potential effect of response order, the scales will be administered in a
369 different order during each session (i.e., FS, FAS, CR10 at min 2; FAS, CR10, FS at
370 min 4; CR10, FS, FAS at min 6; FS, FAS, CR10 at min 8; FAS, CR10, FS at min 10;
371 and CR10, FS, FAS at min 12; Ejelöv & Luke, 2020; Krosnick & Alwin, 1987).

372 **fNIRS Data.** Activity in the dlPFC will be monitored continuously using the
373 MedelOpt® (Seenel Imaging, Amiens, France) fNIRS system and associated ElOpt
374 software. This fNIRS system offers 16 optodes, divided into 8 light sources
375 (light-emitting diode) and 8 detectors (electropods). The selection of the optimal

376 optode montage for the targeted region of interest (i.e., dlPFC) was informed by the
377 fOLD toolbox (Morais et al., 2018). Specifically, a 10-channel model (eight sources and
378 four detectors), including two short channels (one for each brain hemisphere) will be
379 used (see Figure 2). The precise placement of the optodes on the participant's head in
380 relation to the montage will be facilitated with MemoSoft (manufacturer's software).
381 The sampling frequency will be set at 8 Hz to be able to observe the heart rate (HR) in
382 the frequency domain (see Guérin et al., 2026).

383 A marker-based motion capture technique (Qualisys MoCap, Göteborg, Sweden)
384 will be used to detect shifts in the fNIRS headset within each session using the
385 mesh-area method (Guérin et al., 2021). A participant entire dataset will be removed if
386 the shift exceeds 15% in at least one session (for a similar procedure, see Guérin et al.,
387 2026).

388 ***Cardiorespiratory Monitoring.*** HR and respiratory rate will be
389 continuously recorded using an MP150 system, with a BioNomadix® wearable wireless
390 device and a TSD201 respiratory effort transducer (BIOPAC Systems, Goleta, USA).
391 Electrocardiography (ECG) electrodes will be placed according to Einthoven's triangle,
392 an imaginary shape formed around the heart (Barold, 2003). Two electrodes will be
393 placed on each collarbone and a third on the rib cage. The respiratory effort transducer
394 will be placed around the chest wall at the sternal level. The sampling frequency will be
395 set to 250 Hz. Acquisition of ECG and respiratory data will be facilitated using the
396 AcqKnowledge® software. Regarding HRV, root mean square of successive
397 differences (RMSSD) and standard deviation of normal-to-normal RR intervals (SDNN)
398 time-domain indices will be computed based on ECG data (Laborde et al., 2022).
399 Further details can be found in the "Data Pre-Processing" section.

400 ***Behavioural Data.*** Power, RPM, speed and total covered distance will be
401 recorded using a Garmin® Edge 540 device (Study 1). In Study 2, speed and total
402 distance covered will be recorded using the treadmill software (pluto® It sport OEM,
403 COSMED).

404 ***Post-Task Measures.*** After each session, the following variables will be
405 assessed using self-reported questionnaires: remembered pleasure (Visual Analogy Scale;
406 Karageorghis et al., 2025), anticipated pleasure of a future similar active transport
407 session (Empirical Valence Scale; Lishner et al., 2008), session self-efficacy (Welch et al.,
408 2010), self-efficacy towards the use of active transport in a similar environment (Welch
409 et al., 2010)), intention to use active transport in a similar environment (Klößner &
410 Blöbaum, 2010), affective evaluation of the virtual environment, immersion experience
411 (Cutting et al., 2025) and potential cybersickness (Kim et al., 2018). As the
412 participants complete all three conditions within the same laboratory session, it is not
413 possible to determine which condition may have the greatest impact on future
414 behaviour. Therefore, this registered report will not include follow-up measures of active
415 transport behaviour.

416 ***Manipulation Check.*** To assess whether the participants perceived
417 differences across the environment—which is the active ingredient of our experiment—,
418 participants will be asked to indicate their level of agreement with the following
419 statements: “Environments 1 and 2 were different”; “Environments 1 and 3 were
420 different”; “Environments 2 and 3 were different”. Participants will be asked to answer
421 on a scale ranging from 1 (*very strongly disagree*) to 9 (*very strongly agree*). If the score
422 is strictly above 4 (i.e. "slightly disagree"), any differences in the dependent variables
423 across our conditions could be attributed to the perceived presence of these
424 environmental features.

425 Following this, participants will respond to a series of open-ended questions to
426 further explore their perceptions: "What differences did you notice between the
427 environments?", "During the study, what did you understand about the purpose of this
428 experiment?", "Between the odours, sound environment, and visual environment, which
429 element had the most positive impact on your affective experience during the session?
430 Why?", "Between the odours, sound environment, and visual environment, which
431 element had the most negative impact on your affective experience during the session?
432 Why?", "During the session, what elements in the environment did you focus on the

433 most?" These questions will allow us to assess whether participants correctly interpreted
 434 the study's hypotheses and to identify which multisensory elements most influenced
 435 their affective experiences.

436 ***Virtual Environments Check.*** The VR environments' low-level visual
 437 properties (i.e., luminance, contrast, spatial frequencies) will be checked and compared
 438 across conditions, as these could potentially influence perceptual load independently of
 439 the targeted manipulation. To this end, all VR environment screenshots will be analysed
 440 in Python (v3.13.7) using a standardised pipeline. Representative screenshots from each
 441 condition will first be converted to greyscale and resized to 512×512 pixels to control
 442 for dimensional confounds. Following SHINE toolbox guidelines (Willenbockel et al.,
 443 2010), luminance will be quantified as mean pixel intensity and contrast as pixel
 444 intensity standard deviation. Images will be normalised using a linear transformation
 445 approach, following Equation 1.

$$E = Z \cdot S + M \quad (1)$$

446 where $Z = \frac{X-m}{s}$, X is the original image, m is the original mean (luminance), s is the
 447 original standard deviation (contrast), S is the target standard deviation, and M is the
 448 target mean. Target values will be calculated as the average mean and standard
 449 deviation across all conditions, ensuring consistent visual properties without introducing
 450 artificial noise or distortion. Spatial frequency analysis will be performed using 2D Fast
 451 Fourier Transform (FFT) to decompose images into frequency components. Frequency
 452 spectra will be analysed in three bands (low, medium, high) corresponding to coarse
 453 (0-20 cycles/image), medium (20-40 cycles/image), and fine (> 40 cycles/image) visual
 454 details respectively. Dominant frequencies will be identified as the peak energy
 455 components in each spectrum, providing a quantitative measure of the most prevalent
 456 spatial patterns in each condition. Finally, a log-log plot will be generated to describe
 457 the rotational average of the spectra (i.e., the energy at each spatial frequency, in cycles
 458 per image, averaged across all orientations). This will provide a scale-invariant
 459 representation of the spatial frequency distribution that allows direct comparison of the

460 relative power at different spatial scales across conditions (Willenbockel et al., 2010)
461 (see Figure 3 and Supplementary Material 3).

462 To statistically compare low-level visual properties across conditions, a one-way
463 ANOVA will be performed for each property, with associated Tukey’s HSD post-hoc
464 tests when $p < 0.05$. The associated Python and R codes are available on Zenodo
465 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658559>). It should be noted that, while these
466 controls restrict explanations based on differences in perceptual salience between
467 conditions, the perceptual load may still differ across environments, even when the
468 salience is equivalent.

469 **Data Pre-Processing**

470 *fNIRS*

471 To control for the quality of acquired *fNIRS* data, the power-spectral density
472 will be computed using Welch’s estimation method for each participant, condition and
473 channel. The frequency corresponding to maximal peak in the 100–250 beats per
474 minute (BPM) range will be detected in the power-spectral density of the raw *fNIRS*
475 data (for a similar procedure, see Pinti et al., 2019). To guarantee that the identified
476 frequency is the genuine HR frequency, it will be compared to the HR measurements
477 provided by the BIOPAC system, with a tolerance threshold of 10 BPM (Guérin et al.,
478 2023). A channel will be excluded if heart rate frequency is not found in the *fNIRS*
479 signals. An entire participant’s data set will be removed prior to further analyses if all
480 channels pertaining to the region of interest (ROI) is excluded. Any excluded
481 participants will be replaced to ensure that $N = 30$.

482 The presence of the heart pulse is a necessary but not sufficient condition to
483 ensure the quality of *fNIRS* data (Pollonini et al., 2016). Thus, the QT-NIRS toolbox
484 (Quality Testing of Near-Infrared Scans; Hernandez & Pollonini, 2020) will be used to
485 identify channels with poor optical coupling through the computation of the
486 scalp-coupling index (cardiac filter = 2.5–4 Hz; time window = 5 s). For a given
487 participant and channel, *fNIRS* signals characterised by a scalp-coupling index < 0.7
488 for at least 10% of the time will be removed prior to further analyses. As for the

489 power-spectral density check, a participant’s entire data set will be removed prior to
490 further analyses if all channels pertaining to the ROI are excluded. Any excluded
491 participants will be replaced to ensure maintenance of $N = 30$.

492 For the two brain hemispheres, the data coming from the corresponding short
493 channel will be regressed from the collected f NIRS signals from regular channels to
494 account for noncortical hemodynamic responses that represent potential confounds.
495 Correction for motion artefacts will be performed using wavelet filtering (interquartile
496 range = 0.5) in Homer 3 (v1.58.0; Massachusetts General Hospital, Boston, MA). The
497 motion-corrected data will be visually inspected to ensure that the selected interquartile
498 range value is well suited to the f NIRS data. For a given participant, visual inspection
499 will be performed to ensure that no motion artefacts are still be visible in the signal
500 (i.e., high-frequency spikes and/or baseline shifts). To reject both cardiac and breathing
501 rates along with parts of Mayer oscillations, a lowpass filter set at 0.1 Hz will be applied.

502 For each participant and condition, a baseline B and plateau P will be defined
503 as the mean values of oxygenated haemoglobin (HbO_2) upon a 5-s time window starting
504 at the beginning of the condition and upon the last 5 s of the condition, respectively. To
505 estimate the amplitude of changes in oxygenation during a condition, the variations
506 Δ_{HbO_2} will be given relative to its baseline (i.e., by subtracting B to P).

507 *Electrocardiography*

508 To ensure accurate extraction of cardiac metrics, raw ECG signals will be
509 pre-processed on Python (v. 3.13.7) using a systematic pipeline designed to minimise
510 noise and artifacts while preserving physiological fidelity. A 50 Hz Butterworth notch
511 filter will be applied to eliminate electrical line interference. Signal conditioning will be
512 performed using a 4.0 Hz high-pass finite impulse response (FIR) filter (order = 2) to
513 remove baseline wander and low-frequency artifacts (Nguyen et al., 2021). Then, a
514 30 Hz low-pass FIR filter (order = 2) was applied to attenuate high-frequency noise, in
515 line with established protocols (Hu et al., 2020). R-peaks will be identified based on a
516 benchmarking using `neurokit`, `pantompkins1985`, `hamilton2002`, and `emrich2023`
517 methods on Python. Benchmarking test on pilot data showed that the `emrich2023`

518 method was the most accurate (see Figure 4). Therefore, a Visibility Graph-Based
519 Detection method will be used (Emrich et al., 2023; Koka & Muma, 2022).

520 The HR will be extracted using the `nk.signal_rate` function from the
521 `neurokit2` Python library (Makowski et al., 2021), which computes the instantaneous
522 heart rate in BPM based on the intervals between detected R-peaks. The HRV (RMSSD
523 and SDNN) will be extracted using the `nk.hrv_time` function, which computes
524 time-domain HRV metrics from the R-peak intervals.

525 *Respiratory Rate*

526 The respiratory signal will be resampled to 50 Hz using a fast Fourier transform
527 (FFT)-based method (Cole & Voytek, 2019). This resampling rate was chosen as it is
528 sufficient to capture respiratory dynamics without unnecessary computational overhead
529 (BIOPAC Systems, Inc., n.d.). A second-order Butterworth bandpass filter (0.05–1 Hz)
530 will be applied to isolate the respiratory frequency band (BIOPAC Systems, Inc., n.d.).
531 This range will be selected to capture typical respiratory rates (0.06–0.6 breaths per
532 second, equivalent to 3.6–36 breaths per minute; Ansari et al., 2009; Braun, 1990).

533 *Statistical Analyses*

534 *Potential Outliers*

535 Possible outliers will be checked for each statistical model instead of the original
536 data (Leys et al., 2019), using the `performance` R package (Lüdecke et al., 2021). The
537 median absolute deviation (MAD; Leys et al., 2013) will be used to identify univariate
538 outliers, and the Mahalanobis-MCD distance (Leys et al., 2018) will be used to identify
539 multivariate outliers. The threshold for classifying univariate outliers will be set as
540 1.959 (`threshold = list["zscore" = 1.959]`), corresponding to the most extreme
541 2.5% (`qnorm[0.975]`) of observations (Lüdecke et al., 2021).. If the residual
542 distributions of the model with and without the outliers are similar, the outliers will be
543 retained; otherwise, they will be removed (Leys et al., 2019).

544 *Main Analyses*

545 Following descriptive analyses, LMMs with associated contrasts across conditions
546 will be computed to test H_{1-3} . The conditions will be specified as the fixed factor and
547 the participants as the random factor. The LMMs will be built and fitted using
548 maximum likelihood estimation with the `lme4` and `eammeans` R packages (Bates et al.,
549 2015; Lenth & Lenth, 2025). P -values will be approximated using Satterthwaite’s
550 method to estimate degrees of freedom and to provide accurate p -values for fixed effects
551 in models with complex random effects structures (`lmerTest` package; (Kuznetsova,
552 2016; Parma et al., 2023). Effect sizes for fixed effects will be reported using the
553 marginal pseudo R^2 , computed with the `MuMIn` package (Barton, 2018). To address
554 potential non-linear effects of conditions on affective responses, sensitivity analyses will
555 be conducted by extending our primary LMMs to include polynomial terms. Likelihood
556 ratio tests will be used to assess whether the inclusion of quadratic terms significantly
557 improves model fit. Potential exploratory analyses will include age, gender, and BMI as
558 covariates.

559 If no significant differences are found, TOSTs will be performed to test for
560 equivalence (Lakens et al., 2018). The equivalence margins for the TOSTs will be based
561 on the smallest effect size of interest (SESOI; Lakens et al., 2018). The lower (Δ_L) and
562 upper (Δ_U) bounds will be set as symmetric around zero, defined as $\Delta_L = -\text{SESOI}$ and
563 $\Delta_U = +\text{SESOI}$. To determine the SESOI, the small telescope approach will be used,
564 which sets the SESOI to the effect size that would have provided the reference study
565 with 33% power (see Lakens, 2022; Simonsohn, 2015). Specifically, the following
566 equivalence margins will be used:

- 567 • For H_1 : $\Delta_L = -0.10$ (f) or -0.20 (d) and $\Delta_U = 0.10$ (f) or 0.20 (d) (Batistatou
568 et al., 2022).
- 569 • For H_2 : $\Delta_L = -0.16$ (f) or -0.32 (d) and $\Delta_U = 0.16$ (f) or 0.32 (d) (Focht, 2013)
- 570 • For H_3 : $\Delta_L = -0.17$ (f) or -0.34 (d) and $\Delta_U = 0.17$ (f) or 0.34 (d) (Geissler et al.,
571 2021)

572 Statistical assumptions of normality of the residuals, linearity, multicollinearity
573 and undue influence will be checked for all models using the `performance` R package
574 (Lüdtke et al., 2021). In the event of a violation of normality, the data will undergo a
575 normalisation process that will be contingent on the data distribution curves in
576 question (e.g., log10, cube root). The independent variables and potential covariates will
577 be standardised to z-scores.

578 **Pilot Tests**

579 Pilot tests ($n = 9$) were conducted to confirm the logistical feasibility of the
580 proposed experimental protocol and data collection process. Descriptive characteristics
581 of the participants are detailed in Supplementary Material 4 (URL). VR sickness ($M =$
582 $33.92\% \pm 19.64$) and overall protocol acceptability ($M = 5.74 \pm 1.30$ out of 9) were
583 both satisfactory. These results showed that participants were able to complete the full
584 protocol, including wearing the VR and *f*NIRS headsets for 1h30. See Figure 5 for an
585 example of an *f*NIRS time series.

586 **Anticipated Timeline for Completion of the Proposed Set of Studies**

587 If this contribution is accepted for publication, data collection for Study 1 will
588 take place over a period of five months. Data collection for Study 2 will then take place
589 over a further five months, starting after the completion of Study 1 data collection. We
590 estimate that pre-processing and data analyses for each study will take a further two
591 months (a total of four months). Accordingly, we expect to submit the Stage 2
592 manuscript for Study 1 within 10 months of the acceptance of Stage 1 manuscript, and
593 the Stage 2 manuscript for Study 2 within 18 months.

594 **Open Practices**

595 Stage 1 deidentified pilot data and analysis codes have been made publicly
596 available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17658559>). The final dataset,
597 codes and research materials will be made available at the point of Stage 2 submission
598 for Studies 1 and 2.

599

CRedit Author Statement

600

LF: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation,

601

Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualisation,

602

Writing-Original draft, Writing – Review & Editing; SMRG: Conceptualisation, Data

603

curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Project administration, Validation,

604

Visualisation, Writing-Original draft, Writing – Review & Editing; YND-T.:

605

Conceptualisation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration,

606

Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing-Original draft, Writing – Review & Editing

607

Acronyms

608

GHG greenhouse gas

609

BPM beats per minute

610

CR10 Borg Category Ratio-10 scale

611

dIPFC dorsolateral prefrontal cortex

612

FAS Felt Arousal Scale

613

FFT fast Fourier transform

614

FIR finite impulse response

615

fMRI functional magnetic resonance imaging

616

fNIRS functional near-infrared spectroscopy

617

FS Feeling Scale

618

ECG electrocardiography

619

EEG electroencephalography

620

HbO₂ oxygenated haemoglobin

621

HR heart rate

- 622 **HRV** heart rate variability
- 623 **LMMs** linear mixed-effects models
- 624 **MAD** median absolute deviation
- 625 **NS** non-separated traffic
- 626 **VR** virtual reality
- 627 **ROI** region of interest
- 628 **RMSSD** root mean square of successive differences
- 629 **RPE** rating of perceived exertion
- 630 **RPM** revolution per minute
- 631 **S** separated traffic
- 632 **SESOI** smallest effect size of interes
- 633 **SDNN** standard deviation of normal-to-normal RR intervals
- 634 **SN** separated traffic with natural features
- 635 **TOSTs** two one-sided tests

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Table 1

Study Design

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
<p>Could the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with and without natural elements, into virtual urban environments made of concrete lead to a higher affective valence during active transport sessions?</p>	<p>Mean affective valence score $NS < S < SN$ (H_1).</p>	<p>Minimum of $n = 18$ for each study ($f = 0.41$; $\alpha = .05$; $1-\beta = .90$). Total $N =$ as many participants as possible within our time and resource constraints.</p>	<p>LMMs with associated contrasts across conditions. Conditions will be specified as fixed factor and participants as a random factor. Potential covariates are age, gender and BMI. TOSTs if non-significant differences ($\Delta_L = -0.20$ (d), $\Delta_U = 0.20$ (d).</p>	<p>A perceived difference score of ≥ 4 out of 9 between the environments.</p>	<p>The hypothesis will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .050$) and the perceived difference score between the conditions ≥ 4.</p>	<p>Failure to confirm H_1 would call into question the claim that the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with or without natural elements, improve affective valence during an active transport session in an urban environment.</p>

Continued

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
<p>Could the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with and without natural elements, into urban concrete virtual environments during active transport sessions lead to people remembering sessions more pleasurable?</p>	<p>Remembered pleasure score $NS < S < SN$ (H_2)</p>	<p>$n = 18$ for each study ($f = 0.43$; $\alpha = .05$; $1-\beta = .90$). Total $N =$ as many participants as possible within our time and resource constraints.</p>	<p>LMMs with associated contrasts across conditions. Conditions will be specified as fixed factor and participants as a random factor. Potential covariates are age, gender and BMI. TOSTs if non-significant differences ($\Delta_L = -0.20$ (d), $\Delta_U = 0.20$ (d).</p>	<p>A perceived difference score of ≥ 4 out of 9 between the environments.</p>	<p>The hypothesis will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .050$) and the perceived difference score between the conditions ≥ 4.</p>	<p>Failure to confirm H_2 would call into question the claim that the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with or without natural elements, improve remembered pleasure of an active transport session in an urban environment.</p>

Continued

Question	Hypothesis	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
Could the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with and without natural elements, into urban concrete virtual environments lead to a lower cerebral oxygenation of the dlPFC during active transport sessions?	Δ_{HbO_2} NS > S > SN (H_3)	$n = 6$ for each study ($f = 1.93$; $\alpha = .05$; $1-\beta = .90$). Total $N =$ as many participants as possible within our time and resource constraints.	LMMs with associated contrasts across conditions. Conditions will be specified as fixed factor and participants as a random factor. Potential covariates are age, gender and BMI. TOSTs if non-significant differences ($\Delta_L = -0.20$ (d), $\Delta_U = 0.20$ (d).	A perceived difference score of ≥ 4 out of 9 between the conditions.	The hypothesis will be accepted if the statistical test is significant ($p < .050$) and the perceived difference score between the conditions ≥ 4 .	Failure to confirm H_3 would call into question the claim that the separation of motorised and non-motorised traffic, with or without natural elements, reduce cognitive effort during active transport in an urban environment.

Note. NS = non-separated traffic condition; S = separated traffic condition; SN = separated traffic and natural features condition. Statistical power, planned analyses and critical statistical tests for each research hypothesis. dlPFC = dorsolateral prefrontal cortex; LMMs = linear mixed-effect models; TOSTs = two one-sided t tests.

Figure 1

Visual Overview of the Study Procedure

Note. fNIRS = functional near-infrared spectroscopy; HRV = heart rate variability; RPE = rating of perceived exertion. Icon made by Freepik from www.flaticon.com.

Figure 3*Log-Log Plot of Spatial Frequency Spectra*

Note. The log-log plot depicts the rotational average of the spectra across conditions (i.e., the energy at each spatial frequency, in cycles per image, cpi, averaged across orientations). U = urban environment; UC = urban environment with colourful design; UN = urban environment with natural features.

Figure 4*Benchmarking for R-peak Detection*

Note. The data were obtained from a single pilot participant.

Figure 5*fNIRS Time Series*

Note. The data were obtained from a single pilot participant. HbO₂ = oxygenated haemoglobin; U = urban environment; UC = urban environment with colourful design; UN = urban environment with natural features.